

ELECTRONICS INTEGRATED INTO TEXTILES AND ENSURING SUSTAINABILITY ISSUES IN THE FUTURE

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Abstract

This is a review article about the properties of manufactured conductive threads, recent application of conductive textiles (i.e., actuators and sensors, piezoresistive pressure sensors) and the challenges for waste management of conductive textiles that we are going to face in the future. Firstly, the carbon black coated conducting threads are less conductive for lower applied voltages, but the threads are sufficient conductive for higher applied voltages. But if we coat the PP, PLA or PP/PLA yarn with PEDOT: PSS solution, it shows good conductivity. Secondly, the textile actuators were made from cellulose fibers that were knitted into fabrics and then coated with conducting polymers, i.e., PEDOT, PPy was used to produce conductive textiles. Then the fabric is inserted in an electrolyte solution containing cations (+), anions (-), and solvent molecules (S). The reduction and oxidation of PPy with external electric power was used to extend and contract the loop successively. Thirdly, Stitched-based SS yarns and a sewing machine were used to create piezoresistive sensors. When integrated into a garment, the sensors can monitor human vital signs and muscle activity. A graphene-based resistive pressure sensor was also reported, which was utilized to monitor human heart rate and elbow movements. As a repercussion, when these products will enter in the mass market, the recycling difficulties will arrive few years later as the current recycling process is not compatible with the waste management of old e-textiles. If we use EPC, RFID and QR code with conductive textiles, it may help to mitigate the waste management problem to a great extent.

Figure 1: Application of Conductive Textiles [source: Textronics: definition, development and characterization of fibrous organic field effect transistors; Lina Rambausek; PhD Candidate/Project Manager, Department of Textiles, Ghent University, Belgium; January 2014 (ResearchGate figure)]

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1. INTRODUCTION

Smart textiles are ones that incorporate functions into the fabric's structure to enable them to perceive environmental stimuli, respond to them, and adapt to them. The stimulus or reaction could have an electrical, thermal, magnetic, or other source. (Sultan Lipol, 2011)

1.1. Conductive Textiles:

A substance in fiber form is a conductive textile fiber (long and very, very thin). Typically, synthetic fibers have a very low conductivity. Other considerations include that the fiber be appropriate for textile applications and for the various textile industry production phases.

The conductive fiber must be washable if the final product must be washable. The fact that the conductive fiber must not hurt the environment is another crucial consideration. Conductive fibers have a variety of known applications, including antistatic, ESD (Electrostatically Dissipative) shielding, heating, and power transfer. Other uses for conductive fibers include signal transmission and sensors.

Additionally, it will be utilized in medical textiles. At least four methods can be used to create conductive fibers:

1. Melt spinning (mixing carbon black, metal powders or conductive polymers with thermoplastics).
2. Dry spinning.
3. Coating of non-conductive materials with different conductive materials. For instance-coagulated polymers, carbon black etc.
4. Inkjet printing. (Choudhry et al., 2021)

By adding additives to the bulk material, either uniformly distributed or, for example, as a surface coating, the conductivity can be increased. Typically, metal is not injected but rather added to non-conducting threads as a very thin conducting thread. The amount of metal thread added can be changed depending on the needs of the maker. When draw ratios are higher during the melt spinning process, the fiber should be less conductive because the density of conductive material will be decreased. But there might be other situations, like as:

Case 1: The fiber may have been amorphous in form prior to drawing, and the carbon black on the surface may not have been aligned; nevertheless, after drawing, the fiber became crystalline, and the carbon black was arranged, which led to a reduction in resistance.

Case 2: The weather can also have an impact. Low operating temperatures will hasten the drying process, reducing carbon black dispersion and increasing the conductivity of the fiber. (If the fiber was crystalline, the assumption may be correct. If it were amorphous, the result would be the opposite).

Static electricity transmission will be a problem when we use these conducting threads to create conductive textiles. It will be created as a result of friction between conductive textiles and human skin. To discharge the static electricity, we therefore require ESD protection clothing underneath. (Sultan Lipol, 2011)

1.1.1. Conductive material

There are at least three ways of producing conductive fibers:

1. Metal
2. Carbon:
 - a. Carbon black
 - b. Graphite
 - c. Carbon nanotube
3. Conductive polymer:
 - a. Polyaniline (PANI)
 - b. Poly (3, 4- ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT)
 - c. Polypyrrole (PPy). Etc.

By adding additives to the bulk material, either uniformly distributed or, for example, as a surface coating, the conductivity can be increased. Typically, metal is not injected but rather added to non-conducting threads as a very thin conducting thread. The amount of metal thread added can be changed depending on the needs of the maker. (Lipol et al., 2016)

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Conductive yarn manufacturing:

Melt spun PP and PLA and combine PP/PLA yarns are insulators and hydrophobic. Due to their hydrophobicity, PP, PLA, and PP/PLA blend yarns do not absorb any chemicals during coating. In a wide range of application fields, from electronics to medicine, surface changes are crucial for interacting with cells, biosensing, and drug delivery. Numerous different substrates can be altered by Polydopamine (PDA), a synthetic eumelanin polymer generated from dopamine. For numerous applications, including nanotechnology and biotechnology, polydopamine serves as a universal surface modification agent. Here, dopamine and a tris HCl solution were used to treat all thermoplastic yarns. Contact angle (CA) study demonstrated that this PDA treatment changed hydrophobic yarns into hydrophilic yarns. Because of their high conductivity, excellent electrochemical properties, promising catalytic activity, ease of handling, and excellent solution processability, inherently conducting polymers (ICPs) like polypyrrole, PEDOT, and polyaniline have gained popularity for producing multifunctional fibers, films, and fabrics. The goal of this project is to create yarn made of stable, conductive thermoplastics (PP, PLA, and blends of PP/PLA) coated with PEDOT: PSS. (Nazmul Islam et al., 2020)

2.2. Actuators:

In the field of current textile research, the concept of textile actuators is a very promising approach. It is feasible to create a new type of textile actuator by merging one of humanity's oldest technologies, textile processing, in this case in the form of weaving and knitting, with new sophisticated materials, such as electroactive polymers. These actuators increase force by connecting single fibers in parallel, increase strain by using stretchable patterns, and can be mass-produced efficiently. This will open up new possibilities for controlling and constructing assistive equipment, such as exoskeleton-like suits with built-in wearable actuators.

The two most common textile processing methods are weaving and knitting. The warp and weft threads in weaving are perpendicular and distinct thread systems that come into close contact and result in a stiff fabric. The threads in knitting are held together by loops that have the potential to be readily deformed. Wearability, pliability, vast surface area, and omnipresence of textiles led to the creation of smart textiles, which combine textiles with other technologies, including electronics. Smart textile supercapacitors, electrodes with a large surface area, and strain sensors have all recently been produced.

Dielectric elastomers, piezopolymers, carbon nanotubes, shape-memory polymers, phase transition actuation, and thermal actuation are just a few of the new actuator technologies that have been documented. They show that organizing these materials is critical for their performance, despite challenges like as high driving potentials, low strain, and thermal kinetics. Carbon nanotube yarns, nylon actuators, and shape-memory alloy (SMA) wires, for example, have been patterned to provide high actuation forces or rotating actuation. (Maziz et al., n.d.)

2.3. Piezoresistive Pressure Sensors in Textile:

Wearable technology is currently trending in the digital world, and sensors are crucial components. The sensors detect changes in the environment, which can be physical, chemical, or any other type of change that the sensors are designed to detect. Actuators, on the other hand, provide information to the user or an external device regarding the change sensed by the sensor. Electronic sensors and actuators are made of inorganic or metallic materials that are either solid or housed in solid housings, making them difficult to embed in textiles. They also lack flexibility, washability, fatigue resistance, and wearing comfort. These restrictions, as well as certain other technological challenges, have necessitated the development of novel materials and engineering approaches to bring the two worlds of electronics and textiles together.

Active and passive sensors are the two types of sensors. The active sensors can convert input energy into detectable output signals without the need for an external power supply, whereas the passive sensors use with support from an external power supply. The majority of textile sensors are passive. Electromechanical and electrochemical wearable sensors are two forms of textile-based wearable sensors that are currently being studied. When a mechanical force is applied to electromechanical sensors, an electric signal is generated, whereas chemical sensors respond to chemical changes. Strain sensors and pressure sensors, for example, are used to monitor a wearer's breathing rate, pulse, muscular activity, and gestures as a result of a mechanical force or a stretch of the body. A pH sensor, on the other hand, may detect changes in sweat and a biomolecular sensor can detect changes in glucose or lactate. Smart clothing with embedded textile-based sensors to measure body temperature, vital signs, and other chemical changes is also being developed by researchers. (Choudhry et al., 2021)

2.4. Application in Sports:

The sportswear industry was one of the first to benefit from Textronics technology. The way athletes are coached and physiologically monitored during games to enhance their performance could be revolutionized by smart gear. Numerous e-textile goods from well-known sporting companies have hit the market, and most of them have rising markets. Consider a smart sock equipped with textile-based sensors that can monitor an athlete's speed, distance, and number of steps. The Sensoria smart sock can help detect running styles that are more likely to cause injuries by examining foot landing approaches. A removable Bluetooth component is used to wirelessly communicate the data to a smart phone application. One of the most significant tools

for a runner to track his or her performance is gait analysis through pressure profiling. Smart shirt and sports bra can be manufactured also. (Choudhry et al., 2021)

2.5 Objectives of the research:

- Which process will be followed, yarn coating with CP then knitting/weaving or fabric coating with CP?
- Is Vapor Phase Polymerization (VPP) the appropriate option for the homogeneous coating of conductive polymers, i.e. PEDOT, Polypyrrole (PPy)?
- If we combine the Metallic fiber with the conductive textiles during weaving or knitting to increase the performance of actuators, will it fit without hazard?
- How can we make the melt-spun CP coated fiber conductive on lower applied voltages?
- How can we protect the melt-spun CP coated fiber from burning on higher applied voltages?
- How can we make the conductive textiles safer to use for human?
- How can we make the conducting sensors from conductive textiles?
- How can we produce conductive thread with evenly distributed conductive materials?
- How can we control electro-mechanical properties of conductive textiles?
- How can we test the properties of conductive threads properly?
- How the recycle workers can sort the e-textile from other products?
- How the recycle workers can disintegrate the electrical parts that are joined by sewing/laminate with the base garments?
- How can we ensure the second hand shopping of e-textiles?

3. THE NECESSARY MATERIALS FOR CONDUCTIVE TEXTILES PREPARATION AND ITS APPLICATION

3.1. Required resources to produce conductive yarn:

For producing Thermoplastic polymers (PE, PP, PLA, PP/PLA etc.), it is required to use Melt Spinning m/c including we need to ensure suitable environment.

Secondly, as conductive materials, the mentioned chemicals were used, i.e. PEDOT: PSS, Polypyrrole, Carbon black.

Lastly, the used M/C or instruments for testing properties of conductive yarn, i.e. Picoammeter, FTIR, SEM, Tensile Testing m/c, Extensometers. (Lund et al., 2018)

3.2. Materials and machines required for textile actuator:

Fiber/ filament: Lyocell cellulose staple yarns, Lycra/ Spandex.

For weaving/ knitting/ Spinning, the used machines were, viz. Rib Circular Knitting Machine, Single Jersey Circular Knitting Machine, Rapier Loom and Melt Spinning M/C with suitable environment.

The essential Chemicals were, i.e. Pyrrole (Py; Sigma-Aldrich), EDOT (H.C. Starck), Lithium bis (trifluoromethanesulfonyl)im-ide (LiTFSI, 99:0%; Sigma-Aldrich), Carbon black, Metallic powders.

The Testing instruments were, viz. Scanning Electron Microscope; The Voltmeter, The Multimeter, Crocodile clips, The fixer, Vapor Phase Polymerisation chamber, Incubator or Dryer, LEGO lever arm, Picoammeter, FTIR, Tensile Testing m/c, Extensometers.

To recycle and reuse the conductive materials, the used options were, namely, Electronic Product Code (EPC), RFID tags, QR codes. (Maziz et al., n.d.)

3.3. Materials and Machines Required for Piezoresistive pressure sensors:

Cotton, Polyester and Stainless steel yarn;

For weaving/ knitting: Rib Circular Knitting Machine, Single Jersey Circular Knitting Machine, Rapier Loom, Socks machine. The Embroidery machine and plain stitch machine are also required. The suitable environment is essential for the research activity.

The used chemicals were, i.e. Graphene oxide, sulphonate dopant, oxidizing agent. The testing instruments were, i.e. Scanning Electron Microscope; The Voltmeter, The Multimeter, Crocodile clips, the fixer, Vapor Phase Polymerisation chamber, Incubator or Dryer, Picoammeter, FTIR, Tensile Testing m/c, Extensometers, Co-efficient of Friction Tester, Martindale abrasion tester, Washing machine. (Wang et al., 2010)

4. THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONDUCTIVE TEXTILES

4.1. Small preliminary experimental measurements:

Resistance measurement of copper wire: Table 1 displays a thin copper wire's resistance as a function of applied voltage. Depending on the voltage supplied, the resistance is what we would anticipate.

Table 1: The resistance of a thin copper wire as function of applied voltage (Lipol et al., 2016)

U ₂ (V)	I (A)	R ₂ (Ω)	U ₄ (V)	R ₄ (Ω)	R ₂ (Ω)-R ₄ (Ω)
0.006	0.039	0.154	*	*	*
0.031	0.256	0.121	0.005	0.020	0.102
0.162	1.300	0.125	0.024	0.018	0.106
0.255	2.290	0.111	0.044	0.019	0.092
0.326	4.620	0.071	0.091	0.020	0.051

For a few different voltages, we measured a copper wire in Table 1 using the two- and four-point measuring methods. The resistance values (R) are linear for the four point measuring method but are not linear for two points. Additionally, we have showed how the results differ for a particular voltage using the methods stated above. It has been noticed that the difference gets less with higher voltages. We can say that the four points approach is preferable since, unlike the two point method, the contact resistances are not taken into account.(Lipol et al., 2016)

4.2. Resistance measurement of a novel conducting thread

Azadeh Soroudi samples – D.R – 4/16, Roll – PE 1292:

Table 2: The resistance is presented as function of the applied voltage. (Lipol et al., 2016)

Sl.	Uin (Volt)	R (Ω)	Sl.	Uin (Volt)	R (Ω)
1	0.001	*	19	70	5.00E+05
2	0.002	*	20	80	5.00E+05
3	0.005	*	21	90	5.01E+05
4	0.01	8.33E+07	22	100	5.04E+05
5	0.02	9.09E+07	23	120	5.00E+05
6	0.05	1.06E+08	24	140	5.19E+05
7	0.1	1.16E+08	25	160	5.16E+05
8	0.2	5.00E+05	26	180	5.14E+05
9	0.5	5.00E+05	27	200	5.26E+05
10	1	4.98E+05	28	220	5.37E+05
11	2	4.96E+05	29	240	5.45E+05
12	5	4.96E+05	30	260	5.42E+05
13	10	4.96E+05	31	280	5.38E+05
14	20	4.97E+05	32	300	\$
15	30	4.97E+05			
16	40	4.97E+05			
17	50	4.97E+05			
18	60	4.98E+05			

N.B: * = Not Measurable, \$ = Burnt.

Figure 2: The resistance, R (Ω) is shown in Y-Axis depending on the voltage, V value in X-axis

According to tables 1 and 2 (& figure 2), conducting threads have a very strong non-linear behavior at voltages below 0.2 V and are, on average, five orders of magnitude less conductive than copper wire. (Lipol et al., 2016)

4.3. Preparation of Melt Spun Conductive Yarn:

Initially, a melt extruder was used to create PP and PLA thermoplastic melt spun yarns at 170°C and 155°C, respectively. Then, a mixture of thermoplastic polymers (50 percent PP and 50 percent PLA) was manually measured, mixed, and added to the hopper of the extruder. The composite thermoplastic melt spun yarn was extruded at 170°C in consideration of the melting points of PP and PLA. The created composite yarn was divided into smaller pieces with a scissor and placed back into the feed hopper for uniform blending. The final composite (PP/PLA) yarn was created by repeating this procedure twice while maintaining the same temperature, rpm, and voltage percentage of the extruder. The take-up speed of consistent yarn production is stated to be around 1 m/min when taking into account the residence duration (3 min), rpm (90), and output voltage (50 V) of the melt extruder.

PDA and Tris HCl were used to chemically alter these hydrophobic yarns to make them more hydrophilic. Hydrophobic yarns made of PP, PLA, and a combination of PP/PLA were submerged in this aqueous solution and shaken for 24 hours at a speed of 55 rpm while at room temperature. The surface-modified yarns were line-dried at room temperature after being rinsed with distilled water for one minute. These hydrophilic, PDA-treated PP, PLA, and PP/PLA blend yarns were submerged in the PEDOT: PSS dispersion for five minutes.

The coated yarns were then let to air dry for 4 hours at room temperature by being hung on a clothes line with wooden clip hangers. Two dip coating cycles of this coating method were performed. In consideration of the flexibility, stiffness, and rigidity of conductive yarns, all thermoplastic yarns were coated twice. While increasing the conductivity, more coating cycles rendered the strands hard and stiff. For use in textiles for wearable applications, stiff and inflexible yarns are not appropriate.

The electric conductivity of conductive PP yarn is increased after the first and second dip coating cycles respectively 0.25 S/cm and 0.75 S/cm. Similar to this; conductive PLA yarn has electric conductivities of 0.17 S/cm and 0.36 S/cm, respectively. Furthermore, before rinsing, the electrical conductivity of blend PP/PLA yarn is 0.24 and 0.67 S/cm, respectively. The number of dip coating cycles raises the coated yarns' electrical conductivity. Each yarn's electrical conductivity has increased by at least two times since the first coating cycle following the second coating cycles. (Nazmul Islam et al., 2020)

4.4. The characteristics of carbon black coated PE yarn:

The average resistance (R) of the five samples (A1, A2, A3, A4, and A5), which can be differentiated by their various colors, has been compared as a function of applied voltages (U) in figure 1. 500V was the maximum applied voltage for the Picoammeter. We measured the current (I) for all applied voltages and used Ohm's equation ($U=IR$) to get the resistance (R). The applied voltage X-axis has a logarithmic scale. For the various voltages, the average resistance (R) of the five samples was indicated on the graph (range: 0.001-500V). The lines have just been added for eye guidance. (Sultan Lipol, 2011)

Figure 2: The resistance (R) against applied voltage (U) curve for the PE 1292 samples with the draw ratios of 4/24 (A1), 4/20 (A2), 4/16 (A3), 4/12 (A4), and 4/8 (A5) is shown in the graph. Different voltages are displayed on the X-axis, while the average resistance of the five samples mentioned above is presented on the Y-axis

4.5. The techniques to prepare textile actuators:

The conducting polymer (CP) Polypyrrole (PPy) has been used to prepare the textile actuators as it deforms to electrical application. When PPy is electrochemically oxidized or reduced at a low potential of 1 to 2 V, it changes volume. The insertion or ejection of ions and solvents into the polymer matrix is the primary cause of the reversible volume change. The CP actuators require an ion source/sink to work since the volume change is based on ion and solvent motion. This could be an electrolytic solution or a solid polymer electrolyte that allows functioning under normal conditions. The cellulose-based fibers as the core material are used here for giving this material class a new variety of functionalization options.

Hydroxyl groups have previously been shown to be effective anchoring locations for the CP poly (3, 4-ethylenedioxythiophene) (PEDOT) and cellulosic material has the functional hydroxyl group. Cellulose materials are biocompatible, compostable, and made with environmentally friendly, renewable chemistry. We should employ cellulose-based (Lyocell) staple yarns that are single (S) (200 mm in diameter) and two-ply twisted (T). We may use common industrial textile production machinery to assemble the yarns into various textile architectures, such as twill 4/4 weave, s/j, and 2:1 rib knitwear.

We could produce the fabrics first and then coat them with the electroactive polymers, similar to the dyeing method commonly employed in textile manufacturing, resulting in metal-free textile actuators and allowing for the fabrication of massive conductive textiles. A chemically synthesized PEDOT “seed layer” is deposited over the fabrics to form a highly electrically conductive surface, allowing the consecutive electrochemical deposition of the functional, actuating PPy layer. The PEDOT-PPy was reduced and oxidized using an alternating voltage of 1.0 and 0.5 V. When the sample is immersed in the electrolyte, it experiences some solvent swelling; consequently, the sample was prestretched with a 1 g weight to remove this initial slack. The fibers contracted and expanded upon oxidation and reduction, respectively, when a square wave potential (+0.5 and 1.0 V) was applied.

In summary, the conductive fabric is submerged in an electrolyte solution including cations (+), anions (-), and solvent molecules (S). The fabric is prestretched to remove the initial slack between the interlooping yarns before the actuation begins. When the PPy is reduced, cations are injected into the yarn, resulting in yarn elongation and loop elongation. If we oxidized the system consists of PPy, it results in shrinkage of the yarn as ions are released and loop contraction. As a consequence, the fabric is contracted also. (Maziz et al., n.d.)

4.6. The techniques to prepare Piezoresistive pressure sensors

The preparation techniques behind Piezoresistive pressure sensor is mentioned below.

4.6.1. Pressure Sensors

Textile-based pressure sensors employ piezoelectric, capacitive, and resistive principles. They generate an electric signal in response to the application of a compressive mechanical force. These sensors are frequently made from fabrics that have been woven with conductive threads or coated with conductive polymers. They alter their resistance, capacitance, or produce an electric charge in response to mechanical force. Depending on its intended purpose, these sensors are essential for achieving the maximum functional and sensing performance in a wearable.

Piezoresistive sensors alter in resistance as a result of variations in the contact area between the conducting materials. To create textile-based piezoresistive sensors, many types of conductive materials (yarns/fabrics) have recently been studied.

They fall under the categories of well processed intrinsically conductive yarns and textiles in general. Intrinsically conductive yarns, which are frequently made of stainless steel (SS), nickel, copper, aluminum, and other metals, are produced using metal yarns or filaments. Similarly, metal yarns are used to create intrinsically conductive materials like copper mesh and SS knitted fabrics.

Specially prepared conductive yarns or fabrics are given their conductivity via additional processing steps like printing or coating. Conductive coatings made of carbon are among the most popular.

The sensors can track muscle activity and vital signs in humans when they are incorporated into clothing. Additionally, a resistive pressure sensor made of graphene that was used to track elbow movements and human heart rate was also described. The graphene oxide (GO) dip-coated polyester fabric created by Lou et al. can be employed as a pressure sensor in plantar measurement and gait-analysis applications because of its wide detection range and high sensitivity. (Choudhry et al., 2021)

4.7. Sustainable issues in the future with conductive textiles

The lithium-ion batteries are used with e-textiles as a power source. These batteries can be charged up again by using grid connected chargers or by harvesting solar cells, thermal generator, piezo components. Batteries are integrated in the fabric in a way that can be removed from the fabric before washing. In addition, the nondetachable water proof fabric may be included with the fabric also.

The waste management of the old e-textiles is not established yet. Moreover, the waste management standard is not same around the world. The current recycling techniques are not successful for collecting and processing the electronic components are attached with e-textiles.

The current technique of waste management is landfilling and incineration. When we shall landfill the e-textiles with the other municipal solid waste, it will be disposed of as a hazardous product. If we do incineration of the old e-textiles, the bottom ash will contain silver which is hazardous. The landfilling or incineration or recycling challenges of old e-textiles are summarized below.

Finding outdated electronic fabrics among other waste for recycling purposes is a difficult task. However, it is feasible to use a few approaches to discover them, such as the electronic product code (EPC), which is contained in a web-based database and contains the material specifications for the recycling company as well as repair instructions. Additionally, the radio frequency information data (RFID) may be affixed to outdated electronic textiles, but this will add an additional electronic component to the fabric. The greatest option at this time is to combine QR codes with e-textiles that provide the necessary messages for recycling. (Köhler, 2013)

4.7.1. The sustainability challenges with e-textiles

The widespread use of electronic textiles will bring in significant e-textile waste a few years down the road. Using present collection and recycling methods, it will be difficult to collect and dump used e-textiles (such as landfilling, sorting, and burning). Trace amounts of rare materials, such as silver, gold, and rare earth elements, are present in textile-embedded electronic components.

These minerals are scattered over vast textile surface areas and are challenging to recover. During recycling and disposal, the presence of hazardous substances in e-textiles may damage the environment and public health. E-textile recycling can lead to issues with occupational health. Because coarse yarn will have less sustainability if power is stored in it, yarn. Therefore, we need to create good finer yarn. E-textiles that are burned or disposed of provide risks to human health and the environment, such as harmful substance emissions. (Köhler et al., 2011)

5. SUMMARY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CONDUCTIVE TEXTILES

According to tables 1 and 2, it can be summarized that conducting threads have a very strong non-linear behavior at voltages below 0.2 V and are, on average, five orders of magnitude less conductive than copper wire.

Figure 2 shows the lower portion of these graphs, where the resistances (R) for the lower applied voltages (from 0.001 to 1 V) were non-linear and high (about $10^7\Omega$ to $10^8\Omega$). It shows that at lower voltages, threads are not conductive. Interesting though, the condition evolved rapidly from 1 V to 500 V. The linear, low resistance was expected to be around $10^5\Omega$. It implies that at higher voltages, threads are conductors.

The carbon black on the fiber may not be dense enough to make the fiber conductive at the lower applied voltages, which could be the cause. It should be noted that carbon black is primarily responsible for the fiber's conductivity. It should be noted that the resistance increased slightly at the last end of the lines in the graphs. The thermal effects on the fiber during an increase in voltage are most likely the cause of these small increases in resistance.

To make a highly electrically conductive surface for the electrochemical deposition of the functional, actuating PPy layer to follow, a chemically produced PEDOT "seed layer" is first deposited over fabric. The sample was pre-stretched with a 1 g weight to reduce this initial

slack since the sample experiences some solvent swelling when it is submerged in the electrolyte. A square wave potential (+0.5 and 1.0 V) was applied, and the fibers reacted by contracting and expanding in response to oxidation and reduction, respectively.

Piezoresistive sensors were made using SS strands that were stitched together using a sewing machine. The sensors can track a person's vital signs and muscle activity when they are incorporated into clothing. Metallic yarns were covered with a carbon-based conductive polymer solution to construct a yarn-based force sensor, which Parzer et al. designed to increase pressure sensitivity.

Additionally, a resistive pressure sensor made of graphene that could track elbow movements and heart rate was revealed. Due to its wide detection range and excellent sensitivity, the coated fabric can be used as a pressure sensor in plantar measurement and gait-analysis applications, according to Lou et al. The chemicals used included sulphate dopant, oxidizing agent, and graphene oxide.

The waste management of the old e-textiles is not established yet. Moreover, the waste management standard is not same around the world. The current recycling techniques are not successful for collecting and processing the electronic components are attached with e-textiles. The current technique of waste management is landfilling and incineration. When we shall landfill the e-textiles with the other municipal solid waste, it will be disposed of as a hazardous product. If we do incineration of the old e-textiles, the bottom ash will content silver which is hazardous. To compensate this problem, we may introduce electronic product code (EPC) that contains the repair instructions and material specification for the recycling company through a web-based database. Moreover, the radio frequency information data (RFID) may be attached with old e-textiles but it will add additional electronic component to the fabric. But the present best solution will be to use QR code with the e-textiles with necessary messages to recycle it.

6. CONCLUSION

The conducting PE threads coated with carbon black is less conductive for lower applied voltages, but the threads were sufficient conductive for higher applied voltages. But PEDOT: PSS coated PP, PLA and PP/PLA yarns are sufficient conductive. The conductive textiles are going to be used widely around the world very soon as it is very popular.

The application as textile actuator and sensor has opened up a huge possibility of conductive textiles as commercial products. The researchers are working regularly to find new technology with conductive textiles.

Consequently, the future sustainability issues of these products must be considered as these products will contain various hazardous chemicals. The current waste management techniques like landfilling, incineration will not be successful for conductive textiles. Rather EPC, RFID and QR code may be implemented.

Conflict of interest:

The authors have no conflict of interest.

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